

Unusual Presentation of Invasive Mole: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Background: Gestational trophoblastic neoplasia (GTN) commonly arises from molar pregnancies but can rarely follow other gestational events, complicating timely diagnosis and treatment. This report discusses an unusual case of high-risk GTN diagnosed as an invasive mole in a 32-year-old woman following a missed abortion.

Case Presentation: The patient presented with persistent vaginal bleeding and irregular menstruation four months post-abortion. Initial investigations revealed elevated β HCG levels (1,971,301 mIU/mL), and imaging, including MRI and CT, demonstrated a large uterine mass with metastatic spread to the lungs. Based on a FIGO score of 10, the patient was classified as high-risk GTN. Treatment with the EMA-CO chemotherapy regimen resulted in a significant regression of uterine lesions, a marked drop in β HCG levels, and resolution of pulmonary metastases.

Outcomes: The patient responded favorably to chemotherapy, with β HCG levels decreasing to within safe limits and imaging confirming tumor regression. Regular follow-up was established, focusing on β HCG monitoring and imaging to prevent recurrence.

Conclusion: This case highlights the challenges of diagnosing GTN in non-molar contexts and the effectiveness of early β HCG monitoring, multidisciplinary management, and EMA-CO chemotherapy in achieving positive outcomes for high-risk GTN with atypical presentations.

Keywords: Gestational Trophoblastic Neoplasia, Invasive Mole, β HCG, EMA-CO Chemotherapy, Multidisciplinary Management

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Introduction

Gestational trophoblastic disease (GTD) encompasses a spectrum of neoplastic conditions originating from abnormal trophoblastic cell growth [1]. These include hydatidiform mole, invasive mole, choriocarcinoma, and placental site trophoblastic tumors. Invasive mole, a rare and locally aggressive form of GTD, typically follows molar pregnancies [2]. However, in certain cases, it can emerge after other types of pregnancies, including miscarriages or term pregnancies, leading to diagnostic challenges and delays in treatment [3]. This case report discusses an unusual instance of an invasive mole in a 32-year-old woman, following a missed abortion, which presented with persistent bleeding and elevated β HCG levels [4,5].

This case emphasizes the importance of early diagnosis, β HCG monitoring, and a multidisciplinary approach to managing high-risk GTN cases with atypical presentations.

2. Patient and Study Details: This report focuses on a single patient, a 32-year-old woman. The study was conducted at Bharti Vidyapeeth Medical College and Hospital, Pune, India, with institutional

ethics approval for case publication. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for the use of her clinical data, imaging, and treatment information for research and publication.

3. Case Report

Presenting Complaints and Relevant History: The patient presented with persistent vaginal spotting and irregular menstruation for approximately four months after a dilation and evacuation (D&E) procedure conducted due to a missed abortion. Her menstrual cycles, which were previously regular, became irregular following the D&E procedure in January 2023, with cycles occurring every two to three months and prolonged bleeding episodes.

On examination, her vital signs were stable (heart rate: 90 bpm, blood pressure: 110/70 mm Hg), and her BMI was calculated at 29.3 kg/m². Physical examination revealed an enlarged uterus (~14 weeks' size) with no active bleeding from the cervical os.

Diagnostic Investigations: Initial laboratory work revealed a markedly elevated serum β HCG level of

1,971,301 mIU/mL, suggesting trophoblastic activity. Further hormonal tests, including thyroid function, were within normal limits, ruling out other endocrine causes.

Advanced imaging studies were conducted for further evaluation:

- **Pelvic MRI:** A large heterogeneous mass measuring approximately 8.1 x 8.2 x 9.4 cm occupied the uterine cavity, extending into the cervix. The lesion displayed hypo-intense T1 and hyper-intense T2 signals with restricted diffusion, consistent with an invasive mole extending to adjacent structures.
- **CT Thorax:** Multiple nodular lesions with ground-glass opacity were observed throughout both lungs, the largest being 11 x 6 mm, indicating probable metastatic spread.

Based on the clinical, biochemical, and imaging findings, the patient was diagnosed with stage III high-risk gestational trophoblastic neoplasia (GTN) with lung metastasis, receiving a FIGO score of 10. This score was determined by the following factors:

- Antecedent pregnancy: abortion (Score: 1)
- Interval from pregnancy to diagnosis: 6 months (Score: 1)

- Pre-treatment serum β HCG: 1,971,301 mIU/mL (Score: 4)
- Largest tumor size: 9.7 x 10 x 14 cm (Score: 2)
- Metastasis site: lung (Score: 0)
- Number of metastases: 5-8 (Score: 2)

The high-risk classification indicated the need for aggressive treatment.

Treatment and Follow-Up Protocol

The patient was started on the EMA-CO chemotherapy regimen, a multi-drug protocol commonly used for high-risk GTN cases. The regimen included Etoposide, Methotrexate, Actinomycin-D, Cyclophosphamide, and Vincristine. Response to treatment was monitored through serial β HCG measurements and imaging. The patient demonstrated a significant decrease in β HCG levels following chemotherapy, with imaging showing regression of the uterine mass and resolution of nodular lung lesions.

Regular follow-up was scheduled to monitor for recurrence, including periodic β HCG testing and imaging assessments.

Figure 1: Pelvic MRI showing the large uterine mass with invasive characteristics.

Figure 2: CT Thorax illustrating nodular lung lesions, indicative of metastatic spread.

Discussion

This case highlights an unusual presentation of high-risk GTN following a non-molar pregnancy, emphasizing the diagnostic challenges in such cases. Invasive mole is primarily associated with molar pregnancies; however, this case demonstrates that GTN can also develop after non-molar pregnancies, complicating diagnosis. Early suspicion based on persistent elevated β HCG levels was essential in identifying the condition.

Role of β HCG Monitoring: β HCG serves as a critical biomarker for diagnosing and tracking GTN. Persistent elevations in β HCG following pregnancy, as observed here, necessitate further investigation to confirm GTN and monitor response to treatment [6].

Significance of Imaging: MRI and CT imaging played essential roles in diagnosing and staging GTN, providing insights into the extent of disease and identifying metastatic spread, guiding the treatment approach.

Chemotherapy and Multidisciplinary Management: The EMA-CO chemotherapy regimen proved effective in managing high-risk GTN, resulting in tumor regression and a decrease in β HCG levels. The collaborative approach involving gynecology, radiology, oncology, and pathology was instrumental in achieving a successful treatment outcome for this patient [7].

Conclusion

This case report presents an unusual occurrence of invasive mole following a missed abortion, demonstrating that GTN can arise from non-molar pregnancies. The findings emphasize the importance of early diagnosis, particularly in cases of prolonged

bleeding and high β HCG levels post-abortion. The efficacy of the EMA-CO regimen and the importance of a multidisciplinary treatment approach are highlighted in managing complex, high-risk GTN cases. Long-term follow-up through β HCG monitoring and imaging is essential for detecting recurrence and ensuring sustained remission.

References

1. Berkowitz, R. S., & Goldstein, D. P. (2009). Gestational trophoblastic disease: Clinical and epidemiological aspects. *Clinical Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 52(1), 12-21.
2. Lurain, J. R. (2011). Gestational trophoblastic disease I: Epidemiology, pathology, clinical presentation, and diagnosis of gestational trophoblastic disease, and management of hydatidiform mole. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 203(6), 531-539.
3. Soper, J. T. (2006). Role of chemotherapy in the management of gestational trophoblastic disease. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 17(6), 869-882.
4. Seckl, M. J., Sebire, N. J., & Berkowitz, R. S. (2010). Gestational trophoblastic disease. *The Lancet*, 376(9742), 717-729.
5. Savage, P. M., Sita-Lumsden, A., Dickson, S., & Fisher, R. A. (2015). The placental site trophoblastic tumor and epithelioid trophoblastic tumor. *Journal of Reproductive Medicine*, 60(11-12), 503-510.
6. Eysbouts YK, Ottevanger PB, Massuger LF, IntHout J, Short D, Harvey R, Kaur B, Sebire NJ, Sarwar N, Sweep FC, Seckl MJ. Can the FIGO 2000 scoring system for gestational trophoblastic neoplasia be simplified? A new retrospective analysis from a nationwide

- dataset. *Annals of Oncology*. 2017 Aug 1;28(8):1856-61.
7. Girda, Eugenia MD; Ferguson, Lindsay MD; Kennedy, Vanessa MD. Unusual Clinical

Presentation of Disseminated Gestational Trophoblastic Neoplasia [19P]. *Obstetrics & Gynecology* 127():p 136S, May 2016. | DOI: 10.1097/01.AOG.0000483548.88616.b8